

→ The pursuit of the nature of light - and EMF - was Newton's top MIMS¹, not gravity or calculus

MESS 0033

MIMS 2.53 - The Consummate Opti-Mystic, Sir Isaac Newton, the genius of MIMS; a study in historical demonstration or trial by fire.

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December 2022

ABSTRACT

In this paper the author examines the sayings of Sir Newton, and ferrets out examples of early MIMS philosophæther at work within Newton's thinking. He links this connection to the future sciences and his advancements to Newton's direct study of light and connection thereby to the Force (F power), and the Aether (A power). The optimism of Newton was all about humility in the face of God's splendidous Creation, and in knowing that humanity will never "know it all" and never be more than a drop in the ocean.

Keywords: Newton - prism - light - Philosophy - truth -

¹ Figure 1 - A letter to R. Bentley, 1692; credit: Newton/unknown

Newton Invented Maths, Einstein Violated It

The obviousness, and seriousness, of what Newton has said in Figure 1 shouldn't be underestimated. It is clear that Einstein was either ignorant of, or chose to ignore, these approbations. The fact that gravitation turned out to be a modified form of the magnetic field equations discovered by Heaviside only underscores the facts as we have said elsewhere, that the Plasma-electromagnetic Force is the Unified Aether Field²; or nothing is. It is clear that charge - the sea of charge - is the real Aether, and in this, we include all the fermions, baryons, leptons, neutrinos, etc. whose forms of charge and spin are strange and quarkish. We include these because *they are charges*, measured not in Coulomb's (usually) but in keV, thus they are *potentials*.

And what was the potential in Newton's time? If not in Gilbert's magnetics, Newton had no access to Volta's batteries, as of yet. So where did he find raw *potential*, as well as obvious sources of tension and current, but being conveyed at such a rate as to be too difficult to measure, in the early 1700s? Light.

Newton invented Calculus³, but Einstein's pseudotensors were invalid right from the start⁴ because they utilized 1st order differential invariants⁵, which do not exist in unimodular coordinates⁶. This was already proven before his time, as of 1901. But Newton created a tool, from inspiration⁷. Where did this inspiration come from? One could positively, without much reservation, say that it was induced into him through his express wish and connection to the Force (*F* power), as he researched and thought about light. As we have already shown, is a circuit⁸, not a particle⁹, which can be modeled using waves.

People have claimed that Einstein was more successful, except they also think Einstein said the speed of light¹⁰ - that is the rate of induction of light in the Aether¹¹ - is a "cosmic speed limit,"¹² when he never said that.¹³ Moreover, macrolensing has never been found¹⁴, and gravity waves¹⁵ (below and within the error margins which are not greater than the variance of the scale of the waves themselves) have never actually been found.¹⁶

Furthermore, no fantastic clocks in space moving at 99% the speed of light have ever happened, and all the relativistic effects measured have had to do with variances in particle speeds and rates of decay, etc., and nothing to do with an actual measure of a "space-time" that was "bent," etc. The public has been greatly deceived, and misled, about what has actually been measured and found, and the Cult of Einstein is heavily engaged and motivated in the spreading of propaganda.

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https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

³ <https://futurism.com/how-and-why-did-newton-develop-such-a-complicated-math>

⁴ <http://dx.doi.org/10.4006/0836-1398-34.4.420>

⁵ Ricci-Curbastro and Levi-Civita, 1901

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/68876325/Response_to_Crothers_Exposition_of_Unimodular_Defect

⁷ <https://www.mathtutordvd.com/public/How-Isaac-Newton-Changed-the-World-with-the-Invention-of-Calculus.cfm>

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/72712372/OpEd_Light_photons_Cannot_Possibly_be_a_Real_Particle

⁹ [I did the double slit experiment at home](#)

¹⁰ [Why No One Has Measured The Speed Of Light](#)

¹¹ <https://ia802209.us.archive.org/32/items/magnetism1small/magnetism1small.pdf>

¹² <https://www.amnh.org/exhibitions/einstein/light/cosmic-speed-limit>

¹³ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/startswithabang/2018/10/09/the-universe-has-a-speed-limit-and-it-isnt-the-speed-of-light/>

¹⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/Discourses-Mathematical-Illustrations-Electrodynamics-Transformations/dp/0963447157/>

¹⁵ [Stephen Crothers: LIGO -- Its Claims for Black Holes and Gravitational Waves | EU2017](#)

¹⁶ [Wal Thornhill: An Examination of "Gravitational Waves" | Space News](#)

Part of that, is a sort of “apologetics” about the history of Newton¹⁷, and his mysticism¹⁸. But why? The entire point of science, beyond eliminating bad hypotheses, is to make discoveries of *new mysteries*, and their actual physical mechanisms. The best way to do this is to hypothesize into the mystical and unknown. That is precisely what Sir Newton did.

Out of the mouth of the Bard

- (1) *“If I have seen further it is by standing on the shoulders of Giants.”*
 - (2) *“I do not know what I may appear to the world, but to myself I seem to have been only like a boy playing on the sea-shore, and diverting myself in now and then finding a smoother pebble or a prettier shell than ordinary, (3) whilst the great ocean of truth lay all undiscovered before me.”*
 - (4) *“I can calculate the motion of heavenly bodies (5) but not the madness of people.”*
 - (6) *“Nature is pleased with simplicity. And nature is no dummy”*
 - (7) *“What we know is a drop, what we don't know is an ocean.”*
 - (8) *“To myself I am only a child playing on the beach, while (9) vast oceans of truth lie undiscovered before me”*
 - (10) *“Gravity explains the motions of the planets, but (11) it cannot explain who sets the planets in motion.”*
 - (12) *“Truth is ever to be found in the simplicity, and (13) not in the multiplicity and confusion of things.”*
 - (14) *“No great discovery was ever made without a bold guess.”*
 - (15) *“This most beautiful system of the sun, planets and comets, could only proceed from the counsel and dominion of an intelligent and powerful Being... (16) This Being governs all things, not as the soul of the world, but as Lord over all; and on account of (17) his dominion (18) he is wont, to be called Lord God παντοκράτωρ or Universal Ruler.”*
 - (19) *“A man may imagine things that are false, but (20) he can only understand things that are true.”*
 - (21) *“If I have ever made any valuable discoveries, it has been due more to patient attention, than to any other talent”*
 - (22) *“He who thinks half-heartedly will not believe in God; but (23) he who really thinks has to believe in God.”*
- Sir Isaac Newton was asked how he discovered the law of gravity. He replied, (24) *“By thinking about it all the time.”*
- (25) *“How came the bodies of animals to be contrived with so much art, and for what ends were their several parts?*
 - (26) *Was the eye contrived without skill in Opticks, and the ear without knowledge of sounds?...and these things being rightly dispatch'd, (27) does it not appear from phænomena that there is a Being incorporeal, living, intelligent...?”*
 - (28) *“To explain all nature is too difficult a task for any one man or even for any one age. (29) Tis much better to do a little with certainty & (30) leave the rest for others that come after than to explain all things by conjecture (31) without making sure of any thing.”*
 - (32) *“God without dominion, providence, and final causes, is nothing else but Fate and Nature. (33) Blind metaphysical necessity, which is certainly the same always and everywhere, could produce no variety of things. (34) All that diversity of natural things which we find suited to different times and (35) places could arise from nothing but the ideas and (36) will of a Being necessarily existing.”*

¹⁷ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg19025461-500-alchemy-isaac-newtons-curse/>

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Isaac_Newton%27s_occult_studies

(37) "Whence arises all that order and beauty we see in the world?"

(38) "Plato is my friend, Aristotle is my friend, but (39) my greatest friend is truth." (sic)

Responses to the Opti-mystic

Has there ever been a fresher breath of air, than the words of a man 400 years ago? So much of what he has said is still resonant, particularly about the nature and role of Science. Yet, how many have complicated the Natural Philosophæ and made a mess of physics? So that we here in EPEMC must simplify the Force so that we can make a MESS of the cross-threads, and leave a numbering system which encourages precisely as he has said: an endless ocean of undiscovered areas to study. The seeming attitude throughout this Unlightenment is so different in tenor to the Enlightenment, that even the creators of QED marvel that it exists even now as a "final solution" when it was only ever meant as a stop-gap¹⁹, or layover towards the achievement of the true unification and solution. The issue is hubris, and it comes from the celebrity power and the grants, peer review and the cults²⁰ which say they have "consensus science"²¹ and everyone else is "doubting science" or "attacking science" or "waging a war on science." These are the aphorisms of Scientism²², and they have no place in a mystic's heart, or a man of God's mind, and they really have no place even in critical scientific research. Nevertheless, the author wants to respond to the 39 points above, and make more enlightenment happen. Then, we may speak of his alchemy through opticks.

1. Imagine the humility of being Sir Isaac Newton, and feeling that you are standing upon the shoulders of giants like Francis Bacon, Galileo, Kepler, and Gilbert; this is very inspirational.
2. Again the humility, and self-awareness is really breath-taking, and a very mystical out-take is clearly an early identification of the foundations which now form the MIMS philosophy.
3. Based on PEMF theory of EPEMC, the "vast ocean" will always be an ocean, because everything is fractal. We exist in a single triangle, in a world of Sierpinski triangles.
4. Some have argued that Kepler's laws of motion already contain the data necessary to describe Newton's 'law of inertia.'
5. The actual POS theory 1.0! Absolutely true.
6. Pleased with simplicity is such an odd turn of phrase, it seems to be the same idea as the author's "want of reduction or homeostasis." But we must see, also, that Nature never finishes or stays in homeostasis, and all is turned over and begun again.
7. It isn't even clear that we know the drop, for as we start to understand the water molecule we start to understand we do *not* understand it. There are many behaviors of H₂O and HHO²³, as well as other molecular arrangements which creates so many unique behaviors²⁴. Not simply snowflakes, but many types of polar behaviors. It is unsurprising that the Chinese thought that *shui* described half of Tao very accurately.
8. This theme is not by accident, for Yeshua said, "If ye be not like a child, ye shall not enter the Kingdom."²⁵

¹⁹ Quantum Electrodynamics is rotten at the core

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https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

²¹ <https://www.aei.org/carpe-diem/michael-crichton-explains-why-there-is-no-such-thing-as-consensus-science/>

²² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scientism>

²³ The Fourth Phase of Water: Dr. Gerald Pollack at TEDxGuelphU

²⁴ EZ Water - What Is It, Why Do I Need It and How Do I Make It? Dr. Gerald Pollack

²⁵ Matthew 18:3, Mark 10:15, etc.

9. To many, this is a frightening concept, or an affront to human progress and what we can be proud of. But for ones like Newton and the author, this is something that produces excitement. There is no end to what is possible to study or discover!
10. Partially true; gravity as a catch-all of electrogravitics, conservation of momentum, and magnetic moments in relation to rippling fields, certainly does explain much of the motion; but without deep telescoping, no one can fault Newton for this imprecision. The mysterious 'immaterial' mentioned in Figure 1 is now known: Charge. But what the form of the charge and its various arrangements are, in terms of Newtonian summations, + - + -, n times... well we are not sure of the coefficients, arrangements, or the number of n. So all of this is summarized in a hasty word: gravity. It might have also been called a relationship; via resonance with certain constants and mass-energies, appears to be what keeps you bound to Earth. How lucky for us that Newton found a hasty way to describe this philosophæther.
11. He covers this later in the set of quotes, but suffice it to say we do think that the *L* and *G* powers are well defined as exactly this quality: no one sees it, but we know it is there.
12. Again the author would beg the difference to say simplicity, but the sentiment is similar. It is very Occam's Razor.
13. Yes! The inclusion of so many pseudosciences and fake hypotheses, with *a priori* assumptions made which have not panned out, nor have the presumptions and these assumptions based on (such as Cosmic Background Radiation²⁶ or doppler redshift²⁷) panned out.
14. Forming hypotheses are incredibly important in the creation of MIMS²⁸ and improvement not only of science itself, but of humanity's momentum.²⁹
15. Agreed; having been atheist previously and totally understanding the mainstream positions, both institutionally and as a member of the public, the author is most capable of differentiating between accurate scientific positions and inaccurate, through the precision of comparison and discrimination. This discrimination is not a matter of bigotry, for example against unbelievers. It is the comparison of "this" and "that" to find important differentiations, so that deduction and reduction - derivation³⁰ - are natural and accurate. But the author being syncretic and an inductionalist in science, understands completely the opposite tendency, and the difference in results, in life etc.
16. The $L \leftrightarrow G$ power is as described, the author agrees.
17. Again, outside of the theoretical "everything" or "It All", the author thinks Sir Newton meant, specifically, the mimsical "powers"³¹ and the various regions³², and laws that are directly modulated by the King of Laws: Causality, as well as the *A* power, which the non-metaphysical either call the Void or Heaven, depending on their persuasion... mainstream science, or mainstream religion.
18. The unified pole connects the *L* and *G* powers in the "Big *G*" diagram³³, and therefore has mytho-historical basis, and (consequently³⁴), self-consistency.³⁵

²⁶ The "Cosmic" Microwave Background - Bad Science!

²⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/Seeing-Red-Redshifts-Cosmology-Academic/dp/0968368905>

²⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims?authuser=0>

²⁹ <https://teslauniverse.com/nikola-tesla/articles/problem-increasing-human-energy>

³⁰ Derivation always leads to 0... nothingness.

³¹ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

³² https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life

³³ https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

³⁴ And therefore *also* in support of the *parte facto* of the 8 major laws of the *P* power, and the known physica facts of the Universe. Check and mate, mathematicians.

³⁵ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

19. The author cannot think of a single philosophy invented, previous to MIMS, which is based upon science and the scientific method (acknowledging it as the greatest MIMS ever engineered, albeit needing continual evolution³⁶). A quick search revealed only the “philosophy of science” which is not remotely the same thing, but a form of apologetics for Science,

“Philosophy of science is a branch of philosophy concerned with the foundations, methods, and implications of science. The central questions of this study concern what qualifies as science, the reliability of scientific theories, and the ultimate purpose of science.”³⁷

“Though the field is highly specialized, a few touchstone ideas have made their way into the mainstream. Here’s a quick explanation of just a few concepts associated with the philosophy of science, which you might (or might not) have encountered.

- *Epistemology — branch of philosophy that deals with what knowledge is, how we come to accept some things as true, and how we justify that acceptance.*
- *Empiricism — set of philosophical approaches to building knowledge that emphasizes the importance of observable evidence from the natural world.*
- *Induction — method of reasoning in which a generalization is argued to be true based on individual examples that seem to fit with that generalization. For example, after observing that trees, bacteria, sea anemones, fruit flies, and humans have cells, one might inductively infer that all organisms have cells.*
- *Deduction — method of reasoning in which a conclusion is logically reached from premises. For example, if we know the current relative positions of the moon, sun, and Earth, as well as exactly how these move with respect to one another, we can deduce the date and location of the next solar eclipse.*
- *Parsimony/Occam’s razor — idea that, all other things being equal, we should prefer a simpler explanation over a more complex one.*
- *Demarcation problem — the problem of reliably distinguishing science from non-science. Modern philosophers of science largely agree that there is no single, simple criterion that can be used to demarcate the boundaries of science.*
- *Falsification — the view, associated with philosopher Karl Popper, that evidence can only be used to rule out ideas, not to support them. Popper proposed that scientific ideas can only be tested through falsification, never through a search for supporting evidence.*
- *Paradigm shifts and scientific revolutions — a view of science, associated with philosopher Thomas Kuhn, which suggests that the history of science can be divided up into times of normal science (when scientists add to, elaborate on, and work with a central, accepted scientific theory) and briefer periods of revolutionary science. Kuhn asserted that during times of revolutionary science, anomalies refuting the accepted theory have built up to such a point that the old theory is broken down and a new one is built to take its place in a so-called “paradigm shift.”³⁸*

So we can see that the philosophy of science is really a means of explaining science itself, and that is through various philosophies and philosophical techniques. However, MIMS is a method of

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https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPE_MC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EP EMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

³⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philosophy_of_science

³⁸ <https://undsci.berkeley.edu/the-philosophy-of-science/>

futurization and research³⁹, based upon the scientific method, the Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology, with the rights of extension in EPEMC⁴⁰ according to our grades⁴¹ and standards⁴²; with more self-consistency than the PoS, as well.

20. Unfortunately we have found that mankind has a massive willingness to also understand things that are patently *not true*, such as there being more than XX and XY(Y) genders.
21. The author shares this sentiment 100%, however, the goal of MIMS is to also detect that which no one has seen.
22. The author doesn't mean to brag, but it appears from his position that - as God is Truth + It All + Love, etc. - whether they are preachers, scientists, or hippy gurus, they are all thinking less than half-heartedly about God. Or, about Jesus as the case may be for the person (such as the author).
23. There is no easy way to say this: the author has been atheist and a believer, and there is no doubt: there is nothing but evidence for God. It is a plethora.

Figure 2 - Matrix Algebra proof of God's [obvious] existence; says the Law of Conservation.; credit: author; note the Wu-Dao-Di (0+1=1) inherent *inside* the "word" (not name) of GOD.

24. Indicating, once again the idea that you can connect to the Force and Aether, directly, and get the information thereby - via meditation⁴³ or prayer, as it were, or deep forms of inductive cogitation.
25. Ie: Conscious-led evolution

³⁹ https://www.academia.edu/54428725/How_to_Create_a_MIMS
⁴⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc>
⁴¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/grades>
⁴² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>
⁴³ https://www.academia.edu/66982437/MIMS_4_21_22_White_and_Black_Spaces_in_Meditation

26. Here, for the first time, we are seeing the relation of Newton's own mimsical philosophy to light.
27. There are no people alive today, with better training in philosophæ, philosophæther, or logic, that wouldn't come up with the same conclusion.
28. Someone wake up Mr. Dawkins and Mr. Hawking and inform them that Nature said, "No means no."
29. As is clearly re-iterated in the philosophy of science, at least originally.
30. This is the legacy of EPEMC and MIMS.
31. Meaning no firm conclusions that cannot be overturned no matter the evidence.
32. A strange way of defining Xingming⁴⁴, for surely by nature is meant xing 性, and by Fate he means Destiny, which is ming 命. Does he mean completion of causality? Or more like completion? Unclear for sure. However, he is *definitely* speaking about the five forces of life, the "regions."⁴⁵
33. Blind metaphysical necessity is clearly his "Principia", as in the *P* power, which is as the scientists wish it now through belief: the physics and *their* inferior God (sans consciousness).
34. But as we see variability, even in the constants⁴⁶, and amongst the fractal and non-fractal phenomenon, therefore we must conclude some invisible "hand" (so to speak) at work.
35. That is, *L* power, or consciousness, depending on if you are religious to religions, or towards Scientism; both are dogmatic.
36. Will is associated with the Kidney Yang, and that is the shaoyin+yang Qi; and thus we will see that the Will meant here is the ultimate in remonstrance, power, and **D**etermination.
37. From the 'data vault' of the Law of Conservation, as it interacts with Law of Evolution.
38. And yet Aristotle's ideas became nobody's friend. They were anti-MIMS vis-a-vis hiding the truth about atoms and the non-flat Earth. This is how important philosophy is. The basis of science should be rooted in a more solid philosophy, and from there, the philosophy which is born of science (MIMS) only ever evolves, without losing itself to the POS's⁴⁷ via mere, natural, inevitable, erosion of Change.
39. This is why the Dirac proof of God/Truth is so important, for it reveals that while no one can occupy Truth, if one approaches Truth then one gets as close to God as one can be (while alive).

$$\delta(x) = \begin{cases} +\infty & x = 0 \\ 0 & x \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(x) dx = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) \delta(x - \xi) dx = f(\xi) \quad (3)$$

Optical Truth is Omni-science

The idea of Truth is that it can be seen but not owned or known 100%; well how can Truth be seen (and felt)? It must, needs to be, conveyed via some manner and through some *thing* (see Figure 1). That thing is the

⁴⁴ <http://elementalchanges.com/analytical/alchemy/>

⁴⁵ https://www.academia.edu/86538573/MIMS_2_21_The_Union_of_the_5_and_8

⁴⁶ Rupert Sheldrake - The Science Delusion BANNED TED TALK

⁴⁷ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

æther, and the manner is via circuit relationship, that is fields and connections made. So what can do this, and quickly enough? Only light. Light is the circuit connection that establishes the Truth and then what is seen is 'known' and knowing the Truth, "sets you free."

The idea of omni is "all directions" or "all directed" or "all-directional". It is all three, and all at once. Science itself, taken not as a philosophy, movement, or collectivist semi-coordinated hierarchical organization (a solar system of egos and interests, if you will), is flawless pure rationalism that is unfinishable and occupied by only those as Newton has described. They stand on the shoulders of giants, like patient boys, awaiting new truths to beat upon the short from an ocean of vast, unknown data. And science, in this way is all directional, and mystical. It is everywhere, and in everything. There is a science of cooking, and of child-rearing, and of governance and finance. Whatever there was a demigod or spirits for before, there is now an omniscient science that is connected through all things, and in this science we trust to find our escape from the darkness of ignorance, and the repetition of nescience, and to fill the void of loneliness without necessarily destroying ourselves⁴⁸.

Now if we set the two in equivocation, and divide opticks by omnipotence and science by Truth, then God is in the denominator (inferior position) and the equational factors approach zero; derivation by reduction ad finitum. Of course, we could also split Truth via science and omnipotence to be seen with light, and then God or infinity is in the numerator (top position), and that renders the factors essentially infinite.

Therefore we can live, by using light to study the omnipotent, and seeking the truth via science. But setting science as God is simply preposterous... unless one is willing also to worship a light bulb or one's LED screen! Many appear to, the way they stare into the little devils ('smart' phones). But that's beside the point. No one actively worships the physical object producing the light because that is not God, obviously. Rather, light is a means to see the Truth, and be set free.

Prismatism

The idea of splitting something into its parts is not a new idea; the Greeks attempted this with their philosophies and battles. However, using a crystal and shape - a prism pyramid - to do so was certainly a novel approach to understanding the "speed" or frequencies of light. Eventually, a portion of this was understood. However, the prism has accidentally hidden the real mechanism that we unfortunately have no easier method for examining with. The source (light source) and its connection with the loads (various molecules of the crystal

prism) obviously creates an alteration of the 'speeds' (frequencies) via *transformation*. This transformation is apparently related to the geometry, but the author maintains our grip on why this is happening is probably not complete. There is something mitigating this alteration, in his opinion, and it might be an aspect of the *P* and *N* power communication, connecting it to geometry.

Figure 3 - Sir Newton's prism experiment; credit: Biography.com⁴⁹

⁴⁸ As many who think the 'true' AI will do, when this demi-god of hyper IQ would do, lacking WQ and EQ, or a soul; but without data, in this case it is just fear.

⁴⁹ <https://www.biography.com/news/how-isaac-newton-changed-our-world>

Opti-mysticism

Looking at light as a connection to a circuit - to screens, or the sun, etc. - might help to explain things as disparate as insects' obsession with firelight at night, to the spiritual pursuit of sungazing, etc. We won't know, unfortunately, until we zoom deep into the light connections, the MIMS, and take a mystical tack as Newton did when he "thought deeply" about gravity. Then we will get unique, induced rational and deductive ideas, via the *inductive mechanism*.

Conclusions

The views of Newton are perfectly MIMSical, and this isn't surprising given his excellent track record. What was surprising, however, was to see his coherence to the "Big G" and 8 Laws, 5 powers and 5 forces of life, and even the Chinese concepts of xingming⁵⁰. Since he was an alchemist and a mystic, it shouldn't be surprising, but it was. Nevertheless, it speaks to the fact that MIMS is such a useful philosophy that it actually helps to explain Newton and vice versa: you can use Newton to explain MIMS, as a success measure. His futurization, his advancement of humanity, relates directly to his Christian-based alchemy and philosophæther.

Therefore the author must conclude that the best path to fast-forward MIMSification, and general acceleration or "supercharged" techstack⁵¹, is the systematic use of qualified alchemical systems, like Christianity, Taoism, etc. It has a direct, positive influence, if the inquiries are God-based and science-aligned, to have a spiritual source, and that makes sense in MIMS philosophy. It doesn't make sense in the Cartesian and Nietzchesque scientism which is plastic or materialistic-reductionist, without an inductive or intuitive aspect.

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